

A Tracer Study Among Spud Kasambahay Program Recipients from Sy 2008-2018

“A Success Story of Kasambahay Recipients”

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Abstract:- The recipients/beneficiaries are considered as best evidence of a program effectiveness in terms of development or outcome. Moreover, they are a good source of feedback regarding the program’s relevance to their individual life improvement or progress. This study was conducted to determine the status, improvement of the recipients’ life after taking the Kasambahay program. The study further aimed to gather feedback about the Kasambahay Program that could be used to improve its services. The study used the descriptive research design. The respondents were Kasambahay recipients who had completed the program from SY 2008-2018. They were identified using snowballing technique. A structured, non-disguised questionnaire was used to gather data. Data collected were subjected to basic descriptive statistical tools such as frequency, percentage and rank.

Keywords:- SPUD Kasambahay Program, Community Extension Services, Kasambahay Recipients, Tracer Study, Negros Oriental, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Kasambahay Human Development Program of St. Paul University Dumaguete started last school year 2008-2009, as one of the component program of the university’s social justice and equality advocacy under the Christian Formation - Community Extension Services of the university.

The program focuses on improving the lifelong learning skills and personality of the underserved young people and adults of the City of Dumaguete and its neighboring towns and cities in the province. They were provided with technology skills, housekeeping-hospitality skills, first-aid skills, personality development program, values and moral spiritual development activities and other related skills and knowledge through informal and modular sessions coupled with hands-on and certificates of participation and course completion for their total formation.

Volunteer students and personnel of SPUD-CES through the Paulinian Volunteers for Community Development, HRM-T Society and the Guidance Center were the lead clubs/ organizations in implementing the program.

The program represents another concrete action of the University in cooperation with other concern government, and non-government organizations that recognizes the valuable contribution of household workers in our society. In order to help mitigate the vulnerability of the said sector and make such skills and personality development accessible to them, SPUD provides this program not only recognize the value of domestic workers to the society, but also provides them protection and personal development through skills and literacy trainings.

In this connection, the SPUD-Christian Formation CES team in coordination with Guidance personnel and the rest of the departments, took turns in conducting training on Values, Spiritual and Personality Enhancement, Literacy & Skills Development Workshop to the recipients of the Kasambahay program of SPUD in order for them to develop their personality and would learn some skills in upholding Moral Standards and Value-laden personalities, Good self- Image, Basic Literacy skills, Helping Skills, listening and communicating skills. They were also ushered to give value to formal education and thus, should not limit them and become contented with the present status in life.

➤ Framework

Fig 1 Community Extension Program Framework

The study based on the idea that a program or activity of any organization is anchored on the completers or recipients it produced. The study had sought to investigate the post-kasambahay program experience of the recipients of the Kasambahay Program of St. Paul University Dumaguete, their present employment and activities after being recipient of the program given to them. The researchers conceptualized that the recipients will be able to improve their quality of life and or land a job fitted to their present qualifications considering the training they have obtained. The Kasambahay recipients might be working and the nature of their work are no longer related to being just a plane kasambahay or household helpers.

The corresponding results of the study will serve as concrete feedback for the Community Extension Services Kasambahay Program of St. Paul University Dumaguete and the Voice of the Free to help enhance the program and to help recipients develop a sense of purpose and encourage others to reach their higher potentials. Moreover, the contribution of Kasambahay Program at large has greatly influenced the development addressed to by the academe in order that satisfaction and gratification can be attained (Gandeza, 2002).

Lastly, to sum up 5 Kasambahay recipients were faithful to their employee as household helpers/cook, 67 were employed and one is self-employed.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

This study was conducted to determine the status of the Kasambahay Program recipients of St. Paul University Dumaguete in partnership with the Voice of the Free and SUMAPI from AY 2008-2018.

Specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the profile of the Kasambahay recipients in terms of age, sex, civil status, present occupation; 2) the educational profile of the graduates in terms of highest educational attainment; 3) knowledge and skills acquired from the Kasambahay program; and 4) the employment data of the respondents as to the number of recipients who were employed/unemployed or are still working as house helpers, present occupation and status in their present occupation.

In addition, the study also sought to gather inputs on how to enhance the Kasambahay Program of SPUD.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Research Design*

The descriptive method of research was used in this study to determine the present status of the Kasambahay Program recipients of SPUD from AY 2008-2009 up to 2017-2018.

➤ *Research Size*

The study was conducted in the province of Negros Oriental, particularly in the City of Dumaguete and the neighboring towns in Negros Oriental, Philippines where almost all of the respondents composed of 73 Kasambahay

recipients are living. The lists of the respondents with corresponding addresses were taken from the records of the Community Extension Office of St. Paul University Dumaguete after a letter request to study the data was approved by the VP for Christian Formation.

➤ *Instrumentation*

The data needed in the study were gathered using the structured undisguised survey questionnaire and through individual interview. Accordingly, information that responded to the objectives of the study was considered as input in the data analysis.

➤ *Data Collection*

In the process of collecting the data, the researchers initially examined secondary data from the Community Extension Services. However, there were some information needed in the study that were not available in the data gathered. Hence, the researchers made use of the survey questionnaire prepared. Personal interview, telephone calls and text messaging were used in gathering the data. Furthermore, the snowballing techniques was used in locating the respondents.

SUMAPI leaders also assisted in administering the instruments to the respondents.

The data gathered were sorted and tabulated in Excel format. Interpretation of results was done using frequency, percentages and rank.

III. RESULTS

➤ *Profile of Respondents*

Results in the profile of the respondents showed that the majority of them were in the age range of 21-30 years old (50 or 68.49%), 47 were female (64.38%) and single (54 or 61.6%). This adheres to the reality that the majority of the househelpers or kasambahay are females and in the age range of 21-30 years old. Data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Personal Profile of Respondents

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
61-70	2	2.74
51-60	6	8.22
41-50	2	2.74
31-40	12	16.44
21-30	50	68.49
11-20	1	1.36
Total	73	
Gender		
Male	26	35.62
Female	47	64.38
Total	73	
Civil Status		
Single	45	61.64
Married	25	34.27
Separated	3	4.11
Widow/Widower	0	
Total	73	

➤ *Highest Educational Attainment*

The educational profile of the respondents is an indicator of how they value the importance of acquiring the best education. The data revealed that 34 or 46.58 percent of the Kasambahay recipients had earned their tertiary education; 35 or 47.95 percent were High School Graduates and 4 or 5.47 percent remained in their Elementary Education.

Table 2 Highest Educational Attainment

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary	4	5.47
Secondary	35	47.95
Tertiary	34	46.58
Post-Graduate	0	
Total	73	

Knowledge and Skills acquired from the Kasambahay Program are ranked as follows; Leadership skills, interpersonal relations ranked 1.5th, 4th in rank are faith sharing, computer literacy and basic agri-training, ranked 6.5 are Basic household tips and first aid, recycling activity, and ranked 9.5th are values formation, personality development and Hygiene and Sanitation and HRM Skills.

Table 3 Knowledge and Skills Acquired from Kasambahay Program

Categories	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Values formation	61	83.56	9.5 th
Personality development	61	83.56	9.5 th
Basic household tips and first aid	62	84.93	6.5 th
Leadership training	68	93.15	1.5
Interpersonal Relations	68	93.15	1.5
Recycling activity	62	84.93	6.5 th
Faith sharing	63	86.30	4 th
Computer literacy	63	86.30	4 th
Basic agri- training	63	86.30	4 th
Business and other related livelihood	60	82.19	
HRM skills	61	83.56	9.5 th
Hygiene & sanitation	61	83.56	9.5 th
Guest relations & housekeeping	60	82.19	
Simple cookery	58	79.45	

Data showed that 67 or 91.78 percent of the respondents were employed outside their employer while they were kasambahay recipients, 1 or 1.37 percent is self-employed and 5 or 6.85 percent were house helpers of their employers.

Table 4 Present Status of Employment

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Household helpers	5	6.85
Employed	67	91.78
Self-employed	1	1.37
Total	73	

Table 5 shows the varied occupation of the respondents 9 or 12.33 percent of the respondents were store attendant/bagger/sales lady/cashier and 9 or 12.33 percent working students. 5 or 6.85 percent were in janitorial or housekeeping work, there were 4 or 5.47 percent were still kasambahay or house helpers and 4 or 5.47 percent secretarial job, 3 or 4.10 percent were service crew workers, there were 2 or 2.74% agriculturists, teacher, field organizer, call center agent, driver and massage therapist and the rest became a nun, social worker, Regional Director of the Voice of the Free, Senior Sales Man, Brgy. Treasurer, Specimen Collector, Information Staff, Food Technician, Nursing Aide, Entrepreneur, Brgy. Health Worker, Street Sweeper, OFW, Full-time housewife and Weaving Trainor.

Table 5 Present Occupation

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Nun	1	
Social Worker	1	
Staff of the Voice of the Free	1	
Agriculturist	2	
Agricultural Technician	1	
Senior Salesman	1	
Teacher	2	
Store Attendant/ Bagger/Sales Lady/Cashier	9	1.5
Brgy. Treasurer	1	
Field Organizer	2	
Authorized Specimen Collector	1	
Kasambahay	4	4.5 th
Call Center Agent	2	
Janitorial/ Housekeeping	5	3
Delivery Crew	1	
Secretarial	4	4.5 th
Information Staff	1	
Admin Staff	1	
Sales Representative	1	
Food Technician	1	
Nursing Aide	1	
Security Guard	1	
Driver	2	
Service Crew (Previous Job)	3	6 th
Massage Therapist (Previous Job)	2	
Weaving/Trainor (Center Based)	1	
Criminology Graduate	1	
BS Agriculture (First Year Only)	1	
Sewer/Trainor (Center Based)	1	
Entrepreneur	1	
Butcher	1	
Cook (househelper)	1	
OFW	1	
Full-time Housewife	1	
Working Students	9	1.5
Street Sweeper	1	
Baranggay Health Worker	1	
BIT – Automotive	1	

PH Army Trainee	1	
Total	73	

IV. DISCUSSIONS

As observed majority of the Kasambahay recipients were young and are single individuals. Research and experience confirms that youth are increasingly concerned about both communities of interest or purpose and their own geographical communities. Oates, 2004 a National Consultant on Youth Philanthropy said that they have ideas, skills, and energy to contribute, and tremendous capacity to learn, to serve, and to lead. They are ready to accept more responsibility at younger ages, and are prepared to challenge the status quo and initiate change where they feel it is due.

It also shows that majority of Kasambahay recipients were female with a percentage of 64.38. During the International Women’s Day 2019, Michelle Bachelet said that “When women are empowered, they can claim their rights and access to land, leadership, opportunities and choices, economy grow, food security and can improve current and future generations. This only shows that if women are provided with equal opportunities like that of men, they can contribute to accelerate the present situation in their family, society and the world.

The educational profile of the respondents is an indicator of how they value the importance of acquiring education. The data revealed that 34 or 46.58 percent of the Kasambahay recipients had finished their tertiary education. Staff Writer, 2020 in the article “What is the importance of Education to Youths?” said that Education is important to young people because it provides the youth with tools and critical skills to gain employment and provide themselves and their families in the future. Hence, when young people are provided with opportunities to finish their tertiary education they would always aim high and that, there present situation will not hinder them to pursue great heights. They are willing to learn more on new things as shared by R1 and R7. Another respondent (R8) also shared that she has to strive hard to learn and study in order for her to help augment her family income in the future and respondent 9 said that her education and training obtained will help her enhance her skills. Thus, education for them is very important and is given value.

Extension and community involvement is the key result area which makes the community feels the presence of the institution. It serves as the link between the university and the community. It is the avenue where higher educational institution extends its expertise in line with its programs. It shares the transfer of technology and other extension programs which would assist to alleviate the economic status of its beneficiaries.

As mandated by Philippine Constitution, the higher educational institution shall reach out to educationally deprived communities in order to give meaningful reality to their membership in national society and finally enrich their civic participation in program undertaking (De

Leon 2008). One of the pillars of SPUD is to promote the conduct of relevant extension and community involvement programs/activities to let the community feel the presence of SPUD and to share the Paulinian Mission to the least, the last and the underprivileged.

The respondents perceived that the knowledge and skills acquired from the Kasambahay Programs honed their personality on the aspect of Leadership skills as the one with great impact, interpersonal relations, faith sharing, computer literacy, basic agri-training, basic household tips and first aid, recycling activity, and values formation, personality development and hygiene and sanitation and HRM skills as the least skills learned. Thus, the aim of the Community Extension Services of SPUD through its flagship program dubbed as Kasambahay Program which provides different skills and formation program that is responsive to the needs of the underprivileged contributes to the betterment of their lives and thus, become better partners and citizens of our society.

The skills acquired by the respondents opened their horizon to strive harder to have a bachelor’s degree as it opens up rewarding opportunities that might have otherwise been inaccessible to some of them. Joebert, 2020 says that College graduates see 57 percent more job opportunities than non-graduates, and it is estimated that, by 2020, two-thirds of all jobs will require postsecondary education. According to research by Burning Glass Technologies, two million new jobs posted online per quarter require a bachelor’s degree or higher. For job seekers, these online job postings are a primary tool for finding and applying to available roles. While more than 80 percent of all job openings for workers with a bachelor’s degree or higher are advertised online, only 50 percent of jobs requiring a high school diploma are posted online, making it harder for these workers to connect with prospective employers.

As shown in the result, the educational attainment of the Kasambahay recipients and the skills acquired expanded their access to opportunities, has opened doors and connected them to industry leaders with whom they can share ideas and explore new ventures since 67 or 91.78 percent of the respondents were now connected to other employers after the 10 year tracer study.

Thus, result shows that the kasambahay recipients were now having varied occupation; 9 or 12.33 percent of the respondents were store attendant/bagger/sales lady/cashier and 9 or 12.33 percent working students, 5 or 6.85 percent were in janitorial or housekeeping work, there were 4 or 5.47 percent were still kasambahay or househelpers and 4 or 5.47 percent secretarial job, 3 or 4.10 percent were service crew workers, there were 2 or 2.74% agriculturists, teachers, field organizers, call center agents, drivers and massage therapists and the rest became a nun, social worker, Staff of the Voice of the Free, Senior Sales Man, Brgy. Treasurer, Specimen Collector, Information Staff, Food Technician, Nursing Aide, Entrepreneur, Brgy. Health Worker, Street Sweeper, OFW, Full-time housewife and Weaving Trainor.

Indeed, success is not a matter of luck or accident or being in the right place at the right time. The Kasambahay recipients were practicing the principles that they have learned and have moved them to the front of the line of their lives. They have an advantage of experiencing being a kasambahay or household helper that led them to the winning edge of their lives and career.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Majority of the Kasambahay recipients were youth, female and single individuals.

Thirty five kasambahay recipients were able to finish their tertiary education; 35 were High School Graduates and 4 remained in their Elementary Education.

The skills acquired during the Kasambahay Program are ranked as follows starting from; Leadership skills, interpersonal relations, faith sharing, computer literacy and basic agri-training, Basic household tips and first aid, recycling activity, values formation, personality development and hygiene and sanitation and HRM skills.

Majority of the respondents were no longer kasambahay members, they were now employed and were now having varied occupation and employers. This study highlights the fact that despite poverty, our kasambahay recipients still value education as means to finding better employment opportunities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are recommendations and proposed action areas of intervention and improvement for the Kasambahay program of SPUD.

There is a need to continue the program to help improve the quality of life of kasambahay members.

To encourage and recruit more kasambahay recipients to join the program through the testimonies of the kasambahay graduates.

To encourage the members of SPUD Community and the kasambahay graduates to support the kasambahay program through sharing their knowledge, skills and expertise by providing trainers, speakers and facilitators in the different topics and livelihood training programs to kasambahay recipients who are economically marginalized so that they could find opportunities for other gainful means of living.

To link with government and non-government agencies to support the program and encourage benefactors to sponsor deserving kasambahay to pursue higher education and offer employment to deserving participants.

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APPENDIX

- *Christian Formation Office*
- *Community Extension Services*

Table 6 Kasambahay Human Development Program Tracer: 2020-2021

	NAME	AGE	GENDER	STATUS	POSITION	COMPANY	LOCATION	REMARKS
2008-2009								
1	ABOY, JASON	26	Male	Married	Store Attendant/ Bagger	Cang's Shopping Complex (Daro)	Dgte City	.Former CDW- working student
2	BULFA, AILYN		Female	Single	Social Worker	Private Company	Manila	.Survivor of Child Trafficking .License Social Worker
3	EBO, FRESNAFIN	58	Female	Married	Brgy. Treasurer	Camanjac	Dgte City	.Former VTIP
4	ELLOREN, ELMER	40	Male	Single	Field Organizer	Voice of the Free	Neg. Or.	.Former Working Student
5	PAGULONG, MARIBEL	57	Female	Single	Field Organizer	Voice of the Free	Neg. Or.	.Former VTIP Sewer
6	PIPENNO, MARLENE	65	Female	Widowed	Regional Director	Voice of the Free	Neg. Or.	.Sewer Trainer
7	NAHIAL, JOSEPH	33	Male	Married	Agriculturist	D.A. Province of Neg. Or.	Neg. Or.	.Board Passer .Former SPUD Farm Manager .Former Working Student
8	NAHIAL, JULIA	29	Female	Married	Authorized Specimen Collector	RVS Drug Testing & Medical Clinic	Robinsons Mall, Dgte. City	.College Level .Formerly Employed at Lee Plaza
9	VILLACAMPA, MARY ANN	24	Female	Single Mother	Kasambahay	Mr. Al Gabriel Zamora	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
2009-2010								
1	ABALDE, CHEXTER	24	Male	Single	Call Center Agent	Qualfon	Dgte. City	.College Level .Former Working Student
2	ABOY,	23	Female	Married	Janitorial/ 	City Mall	Dgte. City	.Former CDW

	JERMILYN				Housekeeping	Dgte.		
3	CAGMAT, GAMALEL	27	Male	Single	Delivery Crew	Greenwhich Pizza	Dgte. City	.High School Grad .Former CDW
4	CAMPOS, JEHSON	24	Male	Single	Provincial Agriculturist	Panay Island	Western Visayas	.Graduated Magna Cum Laude – BS Agriculture (NORSU Pamplona Campus .Former DOST Scholar .Licensed Agriculturist .Former Working Student (CDW)
5	CELESTIAL, HAYDEE MAE	26	Female	Single	Secretarial	NORSU – Main (SY 2017-2018 Grad.)	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
6	EBAO, ELTON JOHN	24	Male	Single	Call Center Agent	Qualfon	Dgte. City	.College Level .Former CDW
7	GAJELLOMA, CHRISTOPHER	26	Male	Single	Agricultural Technician	Dept. of Agriculture	Siaton Animal Breeding	.Licensed Agriculturist .Former CDW
8	INTAC JANET E.	35	Female	Married	Nursing Aide	NOPH	Dgte. City	.College Grad .Former OFW (Singapore)
9	TAYHON, BELLA	28	Female	Single	Saleslady	Julie's Bakeshop	Q.C. Manila	.Former CDW .TESDA NC II – Bread and Pastry Productions
10	VAILOCES, ANTHONY	25	Male	Married	Security Guard	Bethel Guest House	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
2010-2011								
1	ABALOS, NOEL	27	Male	Single	Store Attendant	Phil. Wine Mercantile Robinsons Mall	Dgte. City	.College Level .Former CDW .TESDA NC II – Bread and Pastry Productions
2	ADLING, MARIA FE	26	Female	Single	Assistant	Elmido's Dental Clinic	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
3	BALDADO, JEROME	27	Male	Married	LGU – Bindoy (Driver)	LGU – Bindoy	Bindoy, Neg. Or.	.Former CDW .Fruit Carving – Extra Income
4	DUNQUE, RAMEL	39	Male	Married	Senior Salesman	Semigire Corp	Dgte. City	.HS Graduate
5	EMO, IVAN	26	Male	Single	Service Crew (Previous Job)	Atong Kamalig Resto	Dgte. City	.Former CDW .Currently Working in Siquijor
6	LUCERIO, MARK REYNARD	24	Male	Single	Store Attendant	OPPO Company	Robinsons Mall Dgte. City	.College Level .Former CDW .Former Service Crew MAX's Dgte & Yellow

								Cab Pizza (Boracay Island)
7	MAMAC, JYLL	27	Female	Single	Massage Therapist (Previous Job)	Nuat Thai Massage	Valencia, Neg. Or.	.Former CDW .Now Self- Employed Breeder (Ornamental Fish)
8	MIER, IMEE	25	Female	Married	CAED Graduate (SPUD SA)	DepEd Teacher	Neg. Or.	.Former CDW (Mr. Dondee Señeris – Employer)
9	OPOSA, ANNALEE	34	Female	Married	Weaving/Trainor (Center Based)	Doormat	SPUD Kas./Residence	.on call Rag Trainor
10	PACULANANG, RAYMUND	28	Male	Married	Truck Driver	Cabrera Sugar Farm	Siaton Neg. Or.	.Former CDW
11	RAMIRES, ANNA JANE	27	Female	Single	Saleslady	Lee Plaza	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
12	SABANAL, RUEL	25	Male	Single	Criminology	NORSU – Main (SY 2017-2018 Grad.)	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
2011-2013								
1	BINAG, BERTELA	34	Female	Married	On Call Kasambahay	Mrs. Paalan	Sibulan, Neg. Or.	.Currently Active with the KALAH CIDDS project
2	BUENAFE, ERNITA	25	Female	Single	BS Education	COSCA (SY 2017-2018 Grad.)	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
3	CAGMAT, ANDRIO	24	Male	Single	BS Agriculture (First Year Only)	NORSU – Main	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
4	CALUMPANG, REBECCA	25	Female	Single	Sales Repr.	Globe Telecom	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
5	GAJELLOMA, GINA	24	Female	Single	Food Tech	NORSU – Main (SY 2017-2018 Grad.)	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
6	LUCERIO, NICANORA	63	Female	Single Parent	Sewer/Trainor (Center Based)	Shoe coat, Curtains, Seat Covers, Doormat Etc.	SPUD Kas./Residence	.SUMAPI Leader .Attended Sunday Session (Attendance and Documentation)
7	SEDIGO, ELVIRA	47	Female	Married	Entrepreneur	Shoe coat, Doormat, Carenderia, & Sari-Sari Store	Residence (Near School)	.TIP Survivor Assisted by VFFI, DSWD .Trained at SPUD Kasambahay Center
8	VELASCO, JOHN MICHAEL	23	Male	Single	AB Gen	NORSU – Main (SY 2017-2018 Grad.)	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
2013-2014								
1	BINAG,	27	Male	Single	Store Attendant	Robinsons	Dgte. City	.Former CDW

	BERNARD					Mall		
2	LUMAPAY, RACEL	23	Female	Single	Service Crew	Jollibee Robinsons Mall	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
2014-2015								
1	BANSUAN, JOYCE	23	Female	Single	Assistant	Dental Clinic	Q.C. Manila	.ALS Passer .Former OSY .TESDA NC II - Cookery
2	BARRERA, ANGINEY	22	Female	Single	Cashier (Previous Job)	Jollibee Main (Last Employer)	Dgte. City	.Staying at home, having a child .ALS Passer .Former CDW .TESDA NC II - Cookery
3	CABUSOG, CHERINE	24	Female	Married	Saleslady (Previous Job)	Lee Plaza	Dgte. City	.ALS Passer .Former CDW .TESDA NC II – Bread and Pastry Productions
4	LOAYAN, MARIA LUISA	52	Female	Single	Kasambahay	*****	Cebu City	.Current Employer Relative of former employer in Dgte. City
5	MONDING, JOAN	37	Female	Married	Janitorial/ Housekeeping	Help 4 U Agency (Ceres Terminal)	Dgte. City	.Former Housewife
6	PACOLARES, JOLLY	24	Male	Single	Admin Staff	DOLE Dgte. City	Dgte. City	.Former CDW
7	SUMPAMPONG	25	Female	Single	BS Financial Management	NORSU Main	Dgte. City	.Working Student
8	TILOS, FROILAN	25	Male	Single	Service Crew (Previous Job)	Foodnet (Last Employer)	Dgte. City	.ALS Learner – OSY .Active on Church Ministry
2015-2016								
1	ARANETA, JULIET	35	Female	Single Parent	Information Staff	Talay Hotel	Dgte. City	.Crew at YMCA Hotel – Junob Dgte. City
2	DEL CAMPO, ANALOU	32	Female	Married	Janitorial/ Housekeeping	TeleTech	Dgte. City	.ALS Passer .TESDA NC III – Event Management .TESDA NC II – Housekeeping .Doormat Production
3	ELNAS, MARIS	21	Female	Single	Assistant	Dental Clinic	Cebu City	.Former CDW
4	MAG-ORASA, TEOFFY	27	Male	Single	Butchery	Conestoga Ltd Product of Ontario	Canada	.Former Working Student (NORSU)
2016-2017								

1	AMARO, JANET	26	Female	Single	Kasambahay	Manila Area		
2	DEDASE, BRENDA	33	Female	Single	Cook	Sister's House	Dgte. City	
3	OMADLAO, MARIA LIZA	36	Female	Married	Janitress	Supermaster	Dgte. City	
4	OPOSA, MARY JOY	36	Female	Married	OFW	Hongkong		
2017-2018								
1	ALCURIN, JOHANN	25	Female	Single	Nun	O' Carm	Dgte. City	.CDW
2	CALUSCUSAN, ANA MARIE	57	Female	Married	Full-time Housewife		Dgte. City	
3	CATAN, JUNELYN	23	Female	Single	Working Student	NORSU	Dgte. City	.OSY
4	ESPINOSA, JOSH LEIGH	22	Male	Single	Student	ASIAN College	Dgte. City	.OSY .ALS Passer
5	MAPULA, RAM ANGEL	17	Female	Single	Student	Valencia	Valencia	
6	MAPULA, TERESITA	58	Female	Married	Street Sweeper	Brgy. Calayugan	Valencia	
7	MELON, LILIA	56	Female	Married	BHW	Brgy. Calayugan	Valencia	.
8	NOCETE, ROSEMARIE	44	Female	Married	Kasambahay	Franciscan Sisters	Bajumpandan	Hilot Wellness Massage .NC II Holder
9	OMOYON, RHESA	40	Female	Married	On Call Hilot	Camanjac	Camanjac	Hilot Wellness Massage .NC II Holder
2018-2019								
1	AGALA, JESSA	24	Female	Single	BS Accountancy	ACSAT	Dgte. City	.OSY .ALS Passer
2	ASEGURADO, WILSON	28	Male	Single	BIT – Automotive	CIT Moalboal, Cebu	Dgte. City	.CDW .ALS
3	AUDITOR, MARK KLENT	22	Male	Single	ALS Present	SPUD	Dgte. City	.CDW .OSY
4	BAJOT, JUNALYN	26	Female	Single	Cashier	Gun and Dealer	Dgte. City	.ALS
5	ESPAÑO, GERALDINE	25	Female	Single	BS Management Accounting	FU	Dgte. City	.OSY .ALS Passer
6	MARIANO, ANGELOUS JOY	21	Female	Single	BS Business Administration	MDC	Dgte. City	.OSY .ALS Passer
7	RUIZ, JAFFE JOSHUA	23	Male	Single	PH Army Trainee	Cebu Base	Dgte. City	.ALS
	TOTAL OF 73							